

Sustainable provision of data sets and strengthening of research data management via grant funding of KonsortSWD

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Abstract

This paper presents experiences and best practices from the process of providing grants to improve the FAIRness of existing datasets and reviews the results of the projects funded by KonsortSWD – NFDI4Society. KonsortSWD – NFDI4Society, as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), supports the social, behavioral, educational, and economic sciences by providing a portfolio of services and tools for research data management to the scientific community. One cornerstone of this portfolio is the provision of grants to researchers for making existing research data available within the infrastructure of specialized research data centers (RDC) in accordance with the FAIR principles. Enriching existing data corpora by facilitating linkage to other data sources, thereby enlarging the analytical potential of these data sources, is an additional objective. Also, the benefits of providing grants are assessed. Across two founding rounds in 2021 and 2023, a total of 12 projects were granted funding from a total of 60 applications. By spring 2026, these projects published two anonymization concepts and made 10 new data corpora involving 60 data sets available for long-term reuse. This documentation contains appendices with relevant documents generated in the process including the contractual agreement.

Keywords: RDM, Project Funding, Reusability of Data, Secondary Use, Research Data Management, Data Access, Research Data Center (RDC), FAIR Principles, NFDI

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1 Introduction

The availability of research data is essential for scientific research. Given how resource-intensive data generation is, the reusability of data plays an increasingly important role in the scientific research process. The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) describe factors that facilitate data reuse and have therefore become an important criterion when assessing research data.

However, many data treasures in the scientific disciplines related to KonsortSWD – NFDI4Society are not available for secondary use. As a result, neither replication of published results nor reuse for other research questions is possible which can lead to inefficient use of existing research data and sometimes to avoidable over-surveying of certain target groups.

One major reason for limited data sharing is the sensitive nature of many datasets used in social, behavioral, educational and economic research. Because these datasets may contain information that may possibly reveal the identity of data subjects, they are protected by data protection laws. Data collectors often lack knowledge about how to prepare sensitive data for reuse, particularly regarding consent procedures for the use of personal data by third parties and appropriate methods for secure data sharing. Hence, KonsortSWD identified a need to raise awareness for reusability of sensitive data within the KonsortSWD research community, especially among data holders.

Research data centers (RDCs) address these challenges by providing secure access to sensitive data through strict data-protection measures. They anonymize or pseudonymize the data to prevent identification while preserving its scientific value, and they use contractual agreements with data users to prohibit any attempts to reidentify data subjects. This legally compliant provision of sensitive data distinguishes them from other infrastructures such as repositories, which typically provide open, i.e. unrestricted, access to uncurated data.

Raising awareness for reusability is therefore essential to facilitate the transfer of sensitive data sets from the community to suitable research infrastructures, such as RDCs, as outlined in KonsortSWD proposals (Adena et al., 2020; Aßmann et al., 2025). At the same time, researchers need to consider data reuse from the very beginning when planning data collections, especially when collecting sensitive data on people, households or companies, as this requires time, legal preparation, and appropriate resources, including informed consent procedures and suitable arrangements for data provision.

Within the context of RDCs, a subject- and method-specific and thus diverse and tailored infrastructure for the sustainable provision of research data has been established. To link researchers and their data with this infrastructure, KonsortSWD introduced research data management (RDM) grants. This paper provides information on the implementation, acceptance, and results of these grants. Specifically, the grants support the transfer of existing data treasures into the sustainable research infrastructures of RDCs. As a result, other

researchers can access and work with the data through various modes, including download, remote access, or on-site use at an RDC.

RDM grants support researchers in preparing and making available relevant new data collections for secondary use in accordance with the FAIR principles. They enable granted projects to disseminate qualitative or quantitative data treasures previously not archived and to facilitate the linkage of existing data to other sources, thereby increasing their analytical potential. The RDM grants particularly target researchers and research projects that did not originally receive funding for data provision, such as the kind available by the German Research Foundation (DFG). By collaborating with RDCs, researchers can make their data available to the scientific communities while benefiting from the RDCs' professional data management services, thereby enhancing the visibility of their data and the impact of their research.

The RDM grants as a measure to foster sustainable data access, were structured along the first funding period of KonsortSWD into two tendering rounds and involved discussion of the tender conditions by the Executive Board of KonsortSWD, a peer review process involving the Committee for Research Data Infrastructure (FDI Committee)¹ and the Advisory Board of KonsortSWD², and the implementation and administrative support for funded projects by the Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories (LifBi)³ as the responsible member of KonsortSWD, see also Figure 1. The first tender started with a call for applications in February 2021 and was well received in the research community. Eight data projects from various disciplines, institutional origins, and constituting different data types were funded with an overall funding volume of approximately 165,000€ net. Project durations varied between 2 and 12 months and were completed by autumn 2022. The call of the second tender was published in autumn 2023. Four data projects from different disciplines and institutions, covering various data types and topics, were funded, including a follow-up project from the first funding round. The overall funding volume amounted to approximately 116,500€ net and projects ran for 6 to 11 months and were completed by summer 2025.

In the following, the paper gives an overview of the processes and resources required to implement the RDM grants. For this purpose, section 2 describes the processes related to the call, subsequent reactions from interested researchers, procedures for evaluating and selecting applications and setting up contractual matters as well as lessons learned that may benefit others who plan to implement such funding. The need for such funding schemes is evident from the number and variety of proposals submitted, as indicated in section 2. Section 3 provides the results of the projects, their topics, their data sources as well as information on the research potential of these new data products for secondary use. Finally, the paper concludes in section 4 with a critical assessment of the RDM grants' first call and offers recommendations to strengthen the transfer of external data sets to RDCs.

¹ FDI Committee website: <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/about/fdi-committee/>

² Advisory Board of KonsortSWD website: <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/about/konsortswd/advisory-board/>

³ Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories website: <https://www.lifbi.de/en-us/Start>

2 Improving Data Access via Research Data Management Grant Funding

Implementation of the provision of RDM grants started with consulting and determining of eligibility criteria, the structure of the review process and corresponding stakeholders, and the relevant time frames to allow for administrative implementation and processing with regard to implied transfers of resources. The latter involved the expertise from the administration department of LfBi, i.e. the institute's third-party funding office and legal office, providing a process for disbursing funding to applicants under the funding scheme of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, 2023).

Figure 1: Steps in the allocation of ConsortSWD RDM grants and their timeline in the two tender rounds. Light blue=2021 tender round, dark blue=2023 tender round. Source: own illustration.

In order to achieve this goal, eligibility criteria were first defined during the preparatory process for the RDM grants, which were to be used in the grant proposals. These included that the applicant i) must be the holder of the data, ii) must fulfill regulations concerning data protection and data dissemination for scientific purposes, iii) shall outline the relevance of the data to the scientific community, iv) must not have received funding beforehand for RDM purposes, and v) will receive funding under the funding regulations NFDI300 of the DFG. These criteria applied to both rounds of the calls for proposals, see the corresponding call for proposal text as given in appendices A1. Call for Applications – RDM Grants 2021 and A2. Call for Applications – RDM Grants 2023. In addition, the general objectives of the RDM grants were operationalized via the following thematic priorities, i.e. 1) concepts for anonymization for

existing data, 2) (transnational) access to sensitive data for secondary users, 3) high-quality metadata documentation, 4) design of a data management plan, and 5) digital long-term preservation. While thematic priorities 1) to 3) were set in both rounds of calls, priorities 4) and 5) were only subject of the first round of calls, because suitable tools for data management planning had since become available. Additionally, digital long-term preservation was considered the responsibility of RDCs, not individual researchers, making these topics less relevant for the second call, particularly regarding the development of data management plans, see Netscher et al. (2025). The process to elicit these criteria and thematic focuses involved the relevant stakeholders, i.e. the FDI Committee providing the expertise on the handling of the data dissemination processes and the KonsortSWD Executive Board and Advisory Board contributing the perspectives of the research community. Likewise, these stakeholders served as reviewers for the submitted proposals.

Advance notice of the funding opportunity and the call for proposals were distributed through a variety of mailing lists, Twitter and published on different web pages. Judging by the interest shown by potential applicants, the call seems to have reached many data holders. Based on the feedback we received after publishing the call, we recommend allocating resources for consultation of interested parties for the time between publication and the deadline of the call. In addition, the application period should exceed two months, as it had proven to be too short for some data holders to partner up with an RDC for the application. Frequently asked questions related to the maximum amount of funding, how to choose and get in touch with an RDC to prepare the application, for which of the parties funding can be applied (data provider and-or RDC) and to the form RDCs should co-submit the application. These examples illustrate data holders' need for more information regarding the application process, especially for data holders who are unfamiliar with RDCs in general and the RDC landscape in the KonsortSWD disciplines in particular. Information on these aspects should be provided for potential applications, as we did in the corresponding call for the second tender round based on the information of the first round. This reduced information inquiries by interested applicants substantially. Since RDCs are to be actively involved in the application process by data holders, they must also be informed about the application periods so that they are prepared for incoming requests.

A total of 42 applications were received within the first round in 2021, with consultations taking place for further projects that ultimately did not result in submission. Out of 42 applications, eight received funding. For the second round, 18 applications were submitted in 2023, with 4 receiving funding. The applications provided information on the work steps required to prepare the as yet unpublished data for subsequent use. Accordingly, the applications also showed which steps for data publication are often not (or no longer) processed within data collection projects, or for which no resources were requested within the scope of the original data collection project. The following overview may also serve as practical guidance on what can or should be defined in project sub-tasks when it comes to data preparation – both for

researchers in planning data collection and subsequent data publication, and for research funders, in order to gain a good understanding of the necessary steps.

Most applicants requested funding for tasks such as preparing, anonymizing, documenting, and publishing data in order to provide additional data, linked and standardized datasets. The main work steps were data update or extension, re-coding of open data, correction of spelling errors or implausible values, standardization of variable names, connection of different materials, and converting them into different file formats, creating anonymization concepts, performing the anonymization, and creating documentation like codebooks or field reports and publishing the files with a registered DOI and appropriate description on the RDC website. For more details, see table A3 Detailed work steps from the applications in the appendix.

The 42 proposals of the first tender round in 2021 were written in cooperation with 19 RDCs with a planned project duration ranging from 1 to 12 months (maximum possible) with a volume from 5,000€ to 100,000€. They covered a variety of data types (quantitative and qualitative surveys, video, audio, observational notes, text documents, web tracking data, medical and administrative data) from different disciplinary contexts (psychology, sociology, labor economics, educational and political sciences, economics, health and sports sciences, history to name the most common). Overall, the submitted applications were quite heterogeneous in terms of content and scope. In this regard, application templates that facilitate comparability in the review process are recommended.

For the second round in 2023, 18 proposals were written in cooperation with 11 RDCs. As we limited funding per application to a maximum of 30,000€, the funding requested was much more uniform compared to the first round, with volumes ranging from 22,500€ to 30,000€. The specified maximum amount corresponded to the financing of a 0.75 full-time equivalent postdoctoral position for six months. Thus, we also indicated an expected project duration of around 6 months. Submitted project duration ranged from 5 to 11 months, with longer projects planning to increase the working hours of existing employees by less than 0.75 full-time equivalent over a longer period.

The review process was organized by the FDI Committee coordinator. The review process was based on an evaluation scheme that had been developed to assess the content of proposals and to meet the requirements of an evaluation process conducted by a multi-member panel based at different institutions. We used a quantitative scoring system in combination with a free comment field. Between 1 and 5 points could be awarded for each of five evaluation dimensions. The evaluation was done online via the conference management system ConfTool, which automatically calculated rankings of the applications based on the total points awarded by the reviewers, which proved to be very useful. The number of evaluation dimensions was reduced from five to three in the second tender round, as two dimensions had proven to be unclear to the reviewers. As a result, the evaluation criteria were adapted to be more sparing and focused in order to make the evaluation process straightforward and easy for the reviewers. Since the comment field was used very differently, we recommend explicitly asking the reviewers to include a brief justification for the scores assigned. This would also provide

the organizers with justifications, which could be communicated (in an adapted version) to the applicants in the acceptance or rejection letter.

For each proposals, two reviewers were chosen on a voluntary basis among members of the FDI Committee. KonsortSWD's Advisory Board was provided with a simplified evaluation scheme and process, contributing additional reviews. The review process involved the uploading of all application materials, managing the reviewers in the review system, and assigning them to applications to be reviewed. This required resources for licensing and procurement of an online review tool.

Given the reports from the reviewers, the project team of RDM grants served as a managing editor and provided a short list of proposals that was then decided upon by the Executive Board of KonsortSWD. The decision process was accompanied by a check of formal requirements and conformity of requested budget items with eligibility defined according to the DFG funding guidelines. For example, the requested staff costs often did not comply with DFG requirements as personnel costs were not calculated in person-months but in man-hours without specifying the pay groups (TV-L Entgeltgruppen) of the salary classification system used in the German public sector. Also, to allow for a better comparison, an Excel template with person-month schemata and automatic calculation of the overhead, was prepared and provided for the second round to reduce feedback loops with applicants and avoid errors on the part of the submitters. For the final funding decision, the KonsortSWD Executive Board needed firstly the content-related funding recommendations by the FDI Committee and the KonsortSWD Advisory Board and secondly a comparison of the existing funding budget with the requested volumes. In our case, the biggest restriction for funding projects (and thus the main reason for rejection) was that the requested funding amounts exceeded the available budget by a factor of ten in the first round and by a factor of six in the second round. Once the projects had been selected, all applicants were informed in due time and the positive funding notifications were coordinated and sent out along with a sample transfer agreement.

All funded projects provided a final report, and were required to inform the LfBi, as the implementing institute of the RDM grant funding, on behalf of KonsortSWD, about the publication of the corresponding data sets, and to document and substantiate the proper use of the funding in order to enable audits. The transfer agreement drawn up by the LfBi's legal department is set out in Appendix A4. The project-specific transfer agreements set out the project-related timelines and funding amounts and aligns formally with the DFG funding regulations. The transfer agreement presented in the appendix was often slightly adapted to adjust the wording regarding the respective rights and obligations. The phase of contractual coordination between the LfBi third-party funding office, the LfBi legal office, and funding recipients and their institutions typically took a period of several months of reviewing the transfer agreements and the need to specify the unstandardized financial plans. This phase lasted longer than expected. As a result, individual project starts were later than planned – also because the lead time for the human resource management of research institutions (increasing working hours of contracts) takes months. This in turn entailed adjustments to the submitted project schedules. It is therefore recommended that the forwarding contract be made available

at the time of the call for proposals so that it can be reviewed in advance by the applicant institutions. During the project periods, LfBi third-party funding office provided funds in line with standardized processes for transfer of funding. For the entire period from planning the call to billing the last project, close cooperation with the third-party funding office and legal office is necessary in order to assume the role of a funder. Overall, it should be noted that although the RDM grant projects are quite small projects, they can and should be handled as, and aligned to, normal third-party funding schemes. At the same time, this levels the costs and benefits to be generated and allows this kind of project funding to be handled and implemented under any funding scheme.

Our understanding is that the RDM grant projects carried out by KonsortSWD within the framework of the NFDI have also contributed to an understanding of common legal frameworks that can be built upon in the future if data from another institution is to be made available on a long-term basis in the RDC system. The exchange process between data holders and RDCs can also be noted as a positive interim result of the RDM grant funding. Further, based on the mediation provided by the FDI Committee, it was also possible to centrally document which RDCs accredited by the German Data Forum (RatSWD) are statutorily able to ingest and publish external data sets and to develop visibility in the scientific community with regard to such possibilities.⁴ These experiences are also being incorporated into the Helpdesk managed by KonsortSWD.⁵

3 Funded Projects and Project Results

The following chapters summarize the funded projects that were selected in the two rounds of calls for proposals for RDM grants held in 2021 and 2023. They highlight the key objectives, thematic focus areas, (preliminary) outcomes of the selected RDM projects, as well as information on the research potential of these new data products for secondary use. In the appendix, A5. Overview of all projects provides an overview of all twelve projects funded by KonsortSWD including details on published reports and datasets as well as applicants and institutions involved.

3.1. Bilateral Science and Technology Agreements Repository

The aim of the project was to provide a data set of intergovernmental science and technology cooperation agreements (STA). Such bilateral agreements can be both declarations of intent and concrete agreements, e.g. on the protection of intellectual property, the exchange of students and researchers, or the establishment of joint steering committees. Even before the start of the project, a comprehensive data set with information on STA was built up in the period between 2017 and 2021. As part of the project funded by KonsortSWD, the existing

⁴ The following website provides a list of all data centers accredited by the RatSWD, with filter options for data centers that offer external data ingest: <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/services/research/all-datacentres/>

⁵ See also <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/services/research/support/konsortswd-helpdesk/> and <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/services/research/all-datacentres/>.

database was revised, and additional material was added in some cases. In this process, additional information and new full texts of original bilateral agreements were included and corrected or documented (Rüffin, 2021a). The Bilateral Science and Technology Agreements Repository (B-STA-R) data set contains information on 1138 agreements on scientific and technological cooperation, as well as on numerous follow-up agreements, primarily concluded by the G20 and the OECD in the period between 1937 and 2020. Among other things, information on the year of conclusion of the contract, the entry into force, the duration of the agreements, and the existence of full texts of the agreements is documented. There are references to full texts for 850 of the agreements. The database (Rüffin, 2021b) and the codebook can be downloaded at the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (GESIS). In addition, a document explaining the search strategies used to generate the database and the selection criteria used is available (Rüffin & Schreiterer, 2017). All information is provided in English. The B-STA-R data are well suited for research in the field of international relations, science studies, foreign science policy, or historical studies and are publicly available via the GESIS Data Archive. For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects.

3.2. Paying Attention to Attention: Media Exposure and Opinion Formation in an Age of Information Overload

The funding of the project served to prepare and make available a comparative panel survey data set from Germany and the U.S. in combination with web tracking data for scientific reuse. The data come from a study that aimed to examine the impact of online media use on opinion formation and other attitudinal and behavioral outcomes (Munzert, 2022). The two overlapping panel surveys in Germany and the U.S. each comprised approximately 1,500 respondents at the time of the first survey in both countries. In Germany, a total of nine waves were conducted between July 2017 and April 2019, while in the U.S. a total of eight surveys were carried out between July 2018 and March 2019. The surveys took place both before and after the German federal election in 2017 and the U.S. midterm election in 2018, respectively. Access to the survey data for both Germany (Munzert et al., 2022) and the U.S. (Guess et al., 2022) is provided via GESIS. Passive web tracking data, which includes browsing histories on desktop and mobile devices, are also available for a large proportion of respondents in both panels. In addition to the processing, documentation, and provision of the actual data, the project also developed a concept for the transfer of the tracking data to third parties, which should be of interest to other projects with similar intent. At the end of the project, a first, weakly anonymized version of the tracking data was published in addition to the survey data, which, for data protection reasons, can only be used within a guest stay at the GESIS Secure Data Center (Munzert et al., 2022b). Moreover, a white paper establishing a framework for publishing web tracking data was released (Munzert et al., 2023). Further, more anonymized versions of the tracking data requiring less restrictive access controls are being planned. The survey content serves research interests in the fields of political science, communications, media studies, and sociology. The linking of the survey with the web tracking data contributes significantly to the attractiveness

of the database. For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects.

3.3. Harmonizing and Combining Data from the Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries with Data from the Starting Cohort 4 of the National Educational Panel Study

The subject of this project was the consolidation and harmonization of two large-scale panel studies: the “Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries” (CILS4EU) and Starting Cohort 4 of the “National Educational Panel Study” (hereafter: NEPS SC4) into a new data product called “CILS4NEPS”. The aim of the CILS4EU study is to investigate the integration of young people with and without a migration background in four European countries (Germany, England, the Netherlands, and Sweden). The NEPS SC4 substudy examines educational pathways of a starting cohort of ninth graders and their transition into the vocational education system, a higher education program, or the labor market in Germany. There are some commonalities among the studies, which ensure comparability and thus the useful combination of CILS4EU and NEPS SC4. Both data sources refer to the same target population (adolescents, 14–15 years old) and in the case of the German substudy of CILS4EU also to the same population (students in grade 9 in the school year 2010/2011). Furthermore, apart from the oversampling of schools with high proportions of migrants, the sampling of schools in CILS4EU is very closely aligned with that of NEPS SC4. As part of the project work, both data sources were examined for their commonalities, suitable items were identified, and harmonized variables generated where possible. In addition to the harmonized data set, adjusted design weights and comprehensive documentation were created (Dollmann et al., 2025; Dollmann & Horr, 2022). The harmonized “CILS4NEPS” data product, which comprises the data of NEPS SC4, the data of CILS4EU, and the harmonized dataset is made available by the Research Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories (RDC-LIfBi) via remote access after conclusion of a data use agreement (Dollmann et al., 2023). For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects. The consolidation of the two databases expands the research potential for both national research and international comparisons. In the latter case, the data can be used to compare educational and vocational careers of young people in Germany with those in England, the Netherlands, or Sweden. Studies limited to Germany may benefit from increased case numbers for certain groups (ethnic and social), as well as for certain events (transition to certain types of schooling or vocational training), allowing for more differentiated analyses.

3.4. Harmonized Data of the Starting Cohort 4 of the National Educational Panel Study and the Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries - Extension

This project is an extension of the CILS4NEPS project to harmonize and merge the data from NEPS SC4 with the data from CILS4EU into a new data product called “CILS4NEPS-E”. In an initial RDM-funded project, the first three CILS4EU waves were harmonized with the corresponding waves from NEPS SC4 (waves 1 to 6) of the student survey in an ex-post

harmonization (see paragraph 3.3). This has already created a large data potential, allowing for in-depth analyses of school success in grades 9 to 13 as well as early transitions to tertiary education, vocational training, and the labor market. Due to the wealth of data in the original data sets, the possibilities for harmonization have not yet been exhausted. The expansion focused on three key aspects:

Firstly, a key enhancement was the harmonization of competency measurements within the two surveys. Both CILS4EU and NEPS SC4 conducted surveys in the 9th grade on fluid cognitive abilities (reasoning) of the students. Although both surveys use different tests, they both aim to measure the same latent construct and assess reasoning abilities in very similar ways. Therefore, it was possible to harmonize the two instruments using specially developed equating methods. Secondly, an additional extension concerned the harmonization of parent surveys. In both studies – CILS4EU and NEPS SC4 – the parents of the surveyed students were included. This provides additional information about the target child, their family environment, and the parents themselves, enabling in-depth analyses – especially with regard to familial transmission processes. Lastly, harmonization was extended to additional waves of both longitudinal studies (including the two COVID-19 surveys). Harmonizing CILS4EU waves 4 and 5 with the corresponding NEPS SC4 waves 7 and 8 provides further insights into school and career transitions as well as attitudes and living conditions during the COVID-19 pandemic (Arnold et al., 2025). The harmonized data CILS4NEPS-E is exclusively accessible via remote access by the RDC-LIfBi after conclusion of a data use agreement. For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects.

3.5. Health Behavior and Injuries in School Age

The funding of this project was used to make the research data of the study “Health Behavior and Injuries in School Age” (GUS) accessible and available for scientific reuse. The main interest of the study was on injuries suffered by children and adolescents in the school context. Accordingly, the panel study included a detailed questionnaire block on topics such as injury frequency, injury location, and injury type. However, in order to investigate possible factors influencing injuries in the school context, extensive information was also collected from the areas of health and sports, nutrition, school and school route, family, socioeconomic status, and personality. The six waves of the survey were conducted annually from November 2014 to March 2020, with surveys of a total of more than 10,000 students in grades 5 through 10. In addition, survey data are available from school principals on the school context and from interviewers on the survey situation. As part of the project work, the data were carefully processed. For example, additional variables were generated, missing values imputed, and open answers recoded. In addition, the data set was checked for content relevant to anonymization and enriched with metadata. To facilitate the handling of the data set, a number of documentation materials (e.g. questionnaires, data manual, technical report, codebook, study description) were compiled or created (Klocke & Fuß, 2022). The data are provided by the RDC-LIfBi to the scientific community and offer comprehensive research potential in the intersection of education and school, and accident or health research (Klocke et al., 2022). For

more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects

3.6. Anonymization Concept for a Linked Establishment Data Set from Data of the Federal Archives with Data of the IAB

The aim of the project was to create an anonymization concept for a linked data set from administrative establishment data of the Institute for Employment Research (IAB), the research institute of the Federal Employment Agency (BA), and data from the Trust Agency ("Treuhandanstalt") of the Federal Archives in order to make the linked data available to labor market research in line with existing data protection legislation. The IAB establishment data contains – since 1975 for West Germany and since 1992 for East Germany – information on the employment structure, the economic sector, and the location of the establishment, among other things. The data from the Trust Agency, on the other hand, contain extensive information about companies located in the area of the former GDR and their development after 1990. The information was collected after the reunification as part of the transfer of socialist companies to the market economy and handed over to the Federal Archives. The data of the Federal Archives thus complement those of the IAB well in terms of content, and the data structures show similarities, so that the two data sources can be linked in an appropriate way and built up into a historical research data set. To create the anonymization concept, the comprehensive data from the Trust Agency were first screened and suitable comparable variables were selected in two successive steps. The decisions were based on the one hand on the (hypothetical) suitability for labor market research (step 1) and on the other hand on calculated (distribution) ratios (step 2). Variables with increased potential for reidentification of establishments were either already excluded in earlier steps or will only be provided in a coarsened form in the final data set (Mackeben et al., 2022). The completion of further steps (linking, data preparation, and sampling), was financed by the data holders' own resources. The new data product "THA-BHP" (Diegmann et al., 2025b) is available via the Research Data Centre of the German Federal Employment Agency at the Institute for Employment Research (FDZ-BA/IAB). For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects. The new database enables the identification of former GDR companies or their establishments that were privatised by the THA/BvS in the IAB's administrative data. It offers a unique opportunity to obtain detailed information on the development of former GDR companies and to determine factors influencing these developments. Research questions aimed at comparing the FRG and the GDR can also be addressed. The accompanying FDZ data report (Diegmann et al., 2025a) helps researchers assess whether the available data is suitable for their specific research needs.

3.7. Language Situation at the Inner-German Border

The aim of the project was to make data from two studies on the language situation at the inner-German border accessible and available for secondary use. Taken together, this is the largest database on this topic. The attractiveness is additionally increased by the very high density of locations and participants, as well as by the variety of data types. The first study

"Investigations on the language situation in the Thuringian-Bavarian border area" is based on data from 435 participants of different age groups and places of the Thuringian-Bavarian border area, which were collected between 1992 and 1994 with the aim of securing the language data of the region for analyses. The language recordings include, for example, queries on words or sentence structures, readings of prepared text, and data on the individuals, or free narratives on the topic of border opening. The data material of the second study "Speaking about the former inner-German border" was collected between 2013 and 2014 and includes, among other things, speech recordings with autobiographical narrative interviews, queries on the spatial location of speech samples and on the participants' own linguistic region, as well as questionnaires on the social data of 29 people from four locations of the former inner-German border (Palliwoda & Werth, 2022). The two databases were processed by the Archive for Spoken German (AGD) for subsequent use in digital and anonymized form and are available to the scientific public via the Database for Spoken German (DGD). The publication includes the digitized recordings, the associated transcripts and speaker information, as well as accompanying texts on the corpus, which classify it linguistically (Palliwoda, 2025; Palliwoda & Werth, 2025). The data material is particularly suitable for scientific studies in the fields of dialectology, language change research, and the sociology of language. Across disciplines, it offers connecting points for research questions from sociology (e.g. socio-biography), history (especially oral history), and political science (e.g. research on attitudes). For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects.

3.8. Development of the Life Story

The aim of funding this project was to process and disseminate the data from the study "Development of the Life Story" (MainLife), see Köber et al. (2015). The data arising from the MainLife study provide a unique combination of qualitative and quantitative data. The MainLife study examines the development of the ability of individuals to tell a coherent life story and how the retrospective view of one's life changes over time, as well as developmental trajectories across the lifespan. The study, which used a longitudinal design, began in 2003 and included five waves of surveying, each collected four years apart over a total period of 16 years. The age cohorts cover the entire life span (8–80 years). The core of the study consists of uninterrupted narratives of life events, in which the seven most important memories previously asked were integrated. The life narratives were supplemented by standardized quantitative surveys (sociodemographics, self, personality, well-being). In order to make the data available for secondary use, informed consent had to be retrospectively collected from the participants. Finally, 123 of the 152 participants contacted gave their consent. Since life narratives include very sensitive information, a concept for pseudonymization had to be developed as part of the project work (Kemper et al., 2022). The quantitative part of the data was transferred to the GESIS Data Archive and is available to researchers via download (Habermas, 2022a). The qualitative data set (life narratives) is made available via the Research Data Center Qualiservice and can be used on-site in a data security room together with the quantitative data (Habermas, 2022b). For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview

of all projects. Overall, the data can be used to address a wide range of questions from psychology, sociology, cultural anthropology, and linguistics, as well as interdisciplinary issues.

3.9. Mobile Knowledge: The Glocalization of Medical Professional Knowledge and Professional Practice

The study "Mobile Knowledge: The Glocalization of Medical Professional Knowledge and Professional Practice" (Glopro) used audiovisual methods to explore doctor-patient communication in four university hospitals in Germany, China, the Netherlands, and Turkey. Using video recordings, a quasi-experiment was conducted between March 2019 and January 2020 to document how initial conversations between physicians and simulation patients with symptoms of heart insufficiency proceed. The goal was to make the physicians' professional knowledge and practice visible with regard to the challenges of this situation. The archive includes 71 video recordings with associated audio recordings, transcripts, and translations, for which consent forms are available for 64 cases, thus allowing archiving and secondary analysis. In order to make the data available for secondary use, important data management steps had to be carried out retrospectively as part of the funded project work, particularly for the documentation of the database and contextualization. In addition, the data were anonymized, enriched with bilingual metadata, and supplemented with a study report (Weiß & Hollstein, 2022). The research data were digitally archived by the Research Data Center Qualiservice and are divided into four data products according to the place of collection: For Turkey, see Sommer et al. (2021), for People's Republic of China, see Weiß, Sommer, Chen, et al. (2021), for the Netherlands see Weiß, Sommer, Merse, Weingartz, et al., (2021), and for Germany, see Weiß, Sommer, Merse, Störk, et al. (2021). A study report provides detailed information on the project's data acquisition, data processing and data access (Weiß et al., 2022). The data offer a variety of possibilities for secondary analyses, especially in the field of professional research, sociology of knowledge, medical sociology, and health sciences. While the anonymized transcripts are suitable for addressing questions in sociology (e.g., sociology of medicine, interculturality), the video data can be used, for example, for basic research in the sociology of interaction. Furthermore, the data offer great potential for medical didactics, e.g., best practices, as well as problems in doctor-patient communication can be identified. For more details regarding data access, see information provided in table A5. Overview of all projects.

3.10. Notified Mass Layoffs

The subject of this project was preparing a data set on mass layoff notifications for secondary use. This included the creation of an anonymization concept, the linking and standardized processing of employment biographies of employees of affected companies using data from the IAB, and the associated data documentation. In an initial review of the existing project data set, corrections, extensions, and simplifications of the data were conducted. In a technical concept for anonymizing the project data, the handling of real identifiers, numerical information presented in text formats (especially dates), as well as free-text fields and the exclusion classification of observations were defined and carried out. Possible exclusion criteria – such as withdrawn or precautionary mass layoff notifications – were also specified and

condensed into an appropriate format (binary variables) derived from free-text information to be anonymized. The data were linked according to a specially developed technical concept for data linkage with successful linking rates varying by linking approach. The linkage was carried out either by recoding numerical identifiers contained in the data or by matching company names along with address details. While the first approach yields high linking rates as long as the numerical identifiers are available, the latter regularly poses a challenge when linking data from different sources. Overall, roughly 50 percent of the observations contained in the original data set could be linked in this way. Additional linking approaches are applied to the remaining data in order to increase the linking rate (Walz, forthcoming). The resulting data will be made available to the international research community for secondary use via the FDZ-BA/IAB in 2026. It offers previously unavailable information for researching the consequences of mass redundancies on the affected employees in the tradition of Jacobsen, Lalonde and Sullivan (1993). Because data availability and accurate identification of mass layoffs are crucial in this research field, the new data set offers a valuable resource for advanced studies. Leveraging the high-quality, broad scope, and detailed nature of IAB raw data, it enables reliable identification of mass layoffs in Germany without relying on heuristics.

3.11. 20 Years of Protest Survey Data

The project “20 Years of protest survey data” aimed to make systematically collected and previously unavailable data on protests in different countries available for scientific reuse for the first time. The data corpus comprises 31 data sets of surveys conducted at protest events in Germany and Poland since the early 2000s.⁶ The data were collected by the Institute for Protest and Social Movement Studies at protest events between 2003 and 2023 on various topics. Protest survey data, i.e. the results of on-site surveys of demonstration participants, provide event-related information on the motives, attitudes, trust in institutions, voting behavior, and demographic characteristics of protesters. They are based on standardized questionnaires with a common core set of questions and topic-specific additions, which enable comparability with international studies. The data are a valuable supplement to general population surveys and make an important contribution to research on forms of democratic participation beyond elections. In the project “20 Years of protest survey data” four key steps were implemented to prepare the data according to FAIR principles. The data, which had originally been collected in different formats, were standardized, documented, and prepared for reuse with the support of the FDZ ALLBUS (Haunss et al., 2025). The individual studies were then published in the GESIS Data Archive, including DOI assignment. Finally, a standardized workflow was developed to enable future protest data to be processed and published efficiently and compatibly.

The published studies were conducted during protests on the topics of climate change, war and peace, international trade, women’s rights, judicial reforms, national independence, LGBTQ+ rights, national memorial holidays, anti-vaccination movements, and anti-fascism. An

⁶ Some data sets include several surveys of protests at different locations at the same day.

overview table with the survey year and country, topic, and DOI can be found in the appendix, see A6. Overview of data sets from the project “20 years of protest surveys”.

The 31 data sets and their documentation enable researchers to gain deeper insights into the composition of demonstration participants as well as their underlying motives and attitudes.

3.12. Crime in the Modern City

The RDM project aimed to make data from the DFG-funded criminological panel study “Crime in the modern City” (CrimoC) available to the interested scientific public in a suitable infrastructure for secondary analyses. The longitudinal study investigated attitudes and the emergence and development of delinquent and deviant behavior and the associated control processes among adolescents and young adults. Methodologically, a cohort-specific longitudinal design was developed for the first time in Germany and implemented in two West German cities with different social structures – Münster and Duisburg. The data from the Münster study (2000–2003) are already available via GESIS Data Archive. The current project aimed at making the Duisburg data reusable. Between 2002 and 2019, a total of 13 survey waves were conducted in Duisburg – initially on an annual basis, later every two years. The study followed a panel design in which the same individuals were surveyed repeatedly over a period of 17 years, starting at the age of 13 and continuing until the age of 30. Data collection was initially carried out in schools, later by mail or interview. The initial sample comprised over 6,000 young people from 7th grade (n=2,627) and 9th grade (n=3,411), of whom only students from 7th grade were continuously surveyed. Around 2,700 remained until the last wave – a retention rate of over 79%. The study generated 13 cross-sectional data sets and a comprehensive panel data set with over 10,000 variables on topics such as delinquency, victimization experiences, parenting styles, and lifestyle. To ensure data quality, the collected data were comprehensively cleaned, including the removal of erroneous cases and the correction of variable labels. Missing values were recoded systematically, and technical variables that could limit secondary use were removed. The data sets were anonymized in close cooperation with GESIS, whereby potentially identifiable information was eliminated. Finally, a detailed codebook was created to document the data structure and coding. The data are available in SPSS and Stata formats and have been prepared for scientific reuse through consolidated panel coding and careful data preparation (Bendler & Reinecke, 2025). A total of 14 data sets on each panel wave plus an integrated panel data set including all waves are available (for an overview including wave, city and DOI, see A7. Overview of data sets from the project “Crime in the modern city” in the appendix). The publication of the Duisburg data in the GESIS Data Archive is funded by KonsortSWD and enables broad scientific reuse.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

By supporting the publication of previously untapped data corpora or the provision of necessary concepts for anonymization via KonsortSWD’s RDM grants funding, 10 new data corpora involving 60 data sets were made available by spring 2026 in accordance with the FAIR

principles for sustained scientific reuse. Additionally, two anonymization concepts were published. These outputs directly reflect the program's central objective of improving the FAIRness and accessibility of existing datasets within the RDC infrastructure.

The selection of projects was guided by criteria that were operationalized along three key dimensions: the scientific potential for reuse enabled through availability within the RDC setting, the scientific quality of the RDM project, and the appropriateness of requested funding. This operationalization ensured that funded projects aligned with both infrastructural and scientific priorities.

However, given the experience on data use after data publication within the RDC network, it remains too early to assess the actual demand for and reuse of the data promoted via the RDM grants at this stage. This limitation applies particularly to the second funding round, which has not yet fully completed its data publication. Nevertheless, monitoring the uptake of these data sets will be an important task for future evaluations.

With regard to managing the provision of grants, several best practices can be identified from the results of the two calls for proposals. The experience from the RDM grant rounds highlights that effective data publication funding schemes require clear eligibility criteria, early stakeholder involvement, standardized application and evaluation procedures, and realistic planning of administrative and legal processes. Moreover, providing comprehensive guidance to applicants and ensuring close collaboration with RDCs emerge as central best practices for enabling sustainable and FAIR-compliant data sharing. In turn, implementing these measures reduces the administrative burden associated with managing the allocation of grants.

Beyond these procedural insights, in terms of the competencies required to assume the role of a funder, the framework for transferring new data sets into the sphere of an RDC also includes legal procurements and the structural financial setting to provide researchers with a reliable planning framework. The transfer contract of the RDM grants is one outcome that can serve as a prototype for other funding projects (see A4. Transfer contract draft in the appendix). Experience shows that a structural framework with a financial upper limit and a time horizon—which is typically less than one year—aligns expectations on the part of applicants and ensures more homogeneous and thus easily comparable applications. Accordingly, relevant legal and financial expertise is required on the organizational side of RDM funding, which can be provided, for example, by the legal and third-party funding division of an institution.

Beyond these organizational aspects, the findings from the two calls for proposals also point to substantive insights regarding data preparation and infrastructure integration. The use of data management plans for research data, for example through the Stamp service, see Netscher et al. (2025), facilitates the comprehensive incorporation of research data management into project schedules.

In addition, the RDM grant project funding helped to establish the operationalization and implementation of processes that enable the transfer of relevant external data sets to RDCs. In addition to conventional data types such as cross-sectional or panel surveys, video

observations, and audio interviews, the funding also made novel data products available and tested the associated processes. Examples of this include the harmonization of different survey data, see Dollmann et al. (2025), anonymization procedures for linking sensitive establishment data, see Mackeben et al. (2022) and Diegmann et al. (2025a), as well as dissemination and curation of new data types like the web tracking data by Munzert et al. (2023).

The experiences from two founding rounds also provide practical guidance: the RDM funding project helped to provide a detailed overview of the data preparation tasks that typically remain unaddressed after the completion of data collection and analysis and which had not been taken into account in the original project proposals. This overview may serve as a guide for both funders and data collectors in planning and evaluating data preparation tasks (see A3 Detailed work steps from the applications in the appendix).

Overall, the findings point to both benefits and remaining challenges of post-hoc data publication funding. On the one hand, significant scientific potential can be leveraged by integrating existing data sets into the sustainable structures of RDCs. The project successfully demonstrates the core benefit of grant funding, namely enabling otherwise unrealized data reuse.

On the other hand, in order to ensure sustainable data provision and availability, resources and funds that enable such provision must be taken into account directly within the framework of the actual project funding, as is already possible today within DFG funding schemes. In the future, established research funding agencies should make greater use of such opportunities to make funding for data-generating projects contingent on the guaranteed sustainable provision of data through established data infrastructures such as RDCs.

At the same time, the positive experiences from KonsortSWD's RDM grants suggest that continuing such funding at the level of the entire NFDI with regular calls for proposals appears worthwhile and can be an effective tool for demonstrating the long-term benefits of regulated and institutionalized data provision. This seems particularly appropriate until the cultural shift toward routine data sharing has progressed further. Furthermore, providing funding after data has been successfully collected makes funding more effective, as it reduces project risk regarding a successful data collection and ensures that initial indicators of the research potential of the data are available.

Part of this cultural shift also involves a better understanding on the part of data collectors and data infrastructure providers (RDCs) of the costs associated with data sharing and external data ingest, especially when it comes to sensitive data that requires a high level of data curation. Experience with the project proposals received shows that even newer data collection projects allocate insufficient resources for data publication. Furthermore, analytical potentials of completed data collection projects may emerge ex post due to changing framework conditions, societal shifts, events and technological developments that necessitate and enable the scientific reuse of previously unpublished data (e.g., digitization of data). Accordingly, a

funding option for the processing and publication of data for reuse after project completion appears both sensible and necessary.

With the establishment of long-term structures within the NFDI, the FDI Committee provides this key expertise for assessing the potential for reuse. In the future, using RDM grants could be considered as a way to unlock research potential across the NFDI as a whole.

Taken together, the findings demonstrate that targeted RDM grants are an effective instrument for unlocking the reuse potential of existing data, establishing best practices for FAIR data provision, and strengthening the integration of heterogeneous data sources into sustainable research infrastructures.

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Appendices

A1. Call for Applications – RDM Grants 2021

Research Data Management (RDM) Grants – Call for Applications

The Consortium for the Social, Behavioural, Educational and Economic Sciences ([KonsortSWD](#)) as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure ([NFDI](#)) invites researchers to apply for RDM grants. RDM grants shall foster the preparation and provision of relevant and new data corpora for secondary use according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). RDM grants shall hence facilitate dissemination of qualitative or quantitative data corpora that have not been archived or released yet to the scientific community. Also, enriching of existing data corpora in terms of linkage to further data sources and thereby enlarging the analytical potential of data sources is possible. By collaborating with a Research Data Center (RDC), data owners can make their unique data available to the scientific research communities and benefit from RDCs professional data management services to enhance the visibility of their data and the impact of their research.

RDM grant proposals address the following range of topics: 1) design of a data management plan, 2) concepts for anonymisation, 3) (transnational) access to sensitive data for secondary users, 4) high-quality metadata documentation, and 5) digital long-term preservation.

To meet the eligibility criteria for RDM grants, applicants

- must be holder of the data,
- must fulfill regulations concerning data protection and data dissemination for scientific purposes (e.g. consent declarations) in order to archive and publish the data by an RDC,
- shall outline the relevance of the data to the scientific community,
- must not have received funding for RDM purposes from other sources (no other public funding), and
- will receive funding in accordance with the funding regulations [NFDI300](#) of the German Research Foundation (DFG).

Applicants without access to an RDC specialized in their field of expertise can team up with an accredited [RDC](#). In tandem, they apply for an RDM grant providing funds for one data project. If no specialized RDC is available directly for individual researchers, applicants will receive a recommendation concerning a suitable RDC for the proposed project. Administration of RDM grants is provided by the coordination of the task area “Data Access” of KonsortSWD located at the Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories ([L'fBi](#)).

Project proposals (max. 15,000 characters incl. space) will be reviewed by the [FDI Committee](#). They contain a description of the data corpus (collection, content, existing documentation including wording of privacy policy and consent - if applicable) and formulate a concise project plan (milestones) for data preparation and data publication by an RDC. They also include a cost calculation and, if available, a list

of publications based on the data corpus. If arrangements with an RDC exist, the project plan, cost calculation and a letter of interest (LOI) should be coordinated with the RDC.

RDM grant proposals will be evaluated according to the following criteria: 1) the potential scientific contribution of the data, 2) the added value created by the availability of the data according to the [FAIR](#) principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability), 3) the scientific quality of the RDM project, 4) the potential for secondary use, 5) the FAIRness of the project and 6) the appropriateness of the requested funding amount for the FDM project.

A decision on the funding of the requested projects will be based on the recommendations of the FDI Committee in June 2021. Funded RDM projects can start their work from 1 July 2021. We expect applications with funding periods of less than one year. At the end of the project period, applicants are required to document their results, especially with regard to realised or planned data publication.

Please send your application to fdi-office@lifbi.de.

- Deadline for applications: April 30, 2021
- Notice of granting: End of June 2021
- Start of funding period: July 1, 2021 or later

Contact

For more information, please visit <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/konsortswd/services> and feel free to contact

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Who we are

A2. Call for Applications – RDM Grants 2023

Research Data Management (RDM) Grants – Call for Applications

The Consortium for the Social, Behavioural, Educational and Economic Sciences ([KonsortSWD](#)) as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure ([NFDI](#)) invites researchers to apply for RDM grants. RDM grants shall foster the preparation and provision of relevant and new data corpora for secondary use according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). RDM grants shall hence facilitate dissemination of qualitative or quantitative data corpora that have not been archived or released yet to the scientific community. Also, enriching of existing data corpora in terms of linkage to further data sources and thereby enlarging the analytical potential of data sources is possible. By collaborating with a Research Data Center (RDC), data owners can make their unique data available to the scientific research communities and benefit from RDCs professional data management services to enhance the visibility of their data and the impact of their research.

RDM grant proposals address the following range of topics: 1) concepts for anonymization for existing data, 2) (transnational) access to sensitive data for secondary users, and 3) high-quality metadata documentation.

To meet the eligibility criteria for RDM grants, applicants

- must be holder of the data,
- must fulfill regulations concerning data protection and data dissemination for scientific purposes (e.g. consent declarations) in order to archive and publish the data by an RDC,
- shall outline the relevance of the data to the scientific community,
- must not have received funding for RDM purposes from other sources (no other public funding), and
- will receive funding in accordance with the funding regulations [NFDI300](#) of the German Research Foundation (DFG).

Applicants apply in tandem with an accredited [RDC](#) for funding for a research data management project. If no specialized RDC is available directly for individual researchers, applicants will receive a recommendation concerning a suitable RDC for the proposed project. The funding is aimed in particular at cross-location collaborations to provide new data products. Administration of RDM grants is provided by the coordination of the task area “Data Access” of KonsortSWD located at the Leibniz-Institute for Educational Trajectories ([LifBi](#)).

Project proposals (max. 15,000 characters incl. space) contain a description of the data corpus (collection, content, existing documentation including wording of privacy policy and consent - if applicable) and formulate a concise project plan (milestones) for data preparation and data publication by an RDC. They also include a cost calculation and, if available, a list of publications based on the data corpus. If arrangements with an RDC exist, the project plan, cost calculation and a letter of interest (LOI) should be coordinated with the RDC.

RDM grant proposals will be reviewed by members of the [FDI Committee](#) and the [KonsortSWD Advisory Board](#) according to the following criteria: 1) the potential scientific contribution of the data and the added value created by the availability of the data according to the [FAIR](#) principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability), 2) the scientific quality of the RDM project, 3) the appropriateness of the requested funding amount for the FDM project.

Funded FDM projects can start their work from October 1, 2024 and must have completed it by August 31, 2025. Funding per application comprises a maximum of EUR 30,000 (plus 22% DFG program allowance, provided the applicant institution has adopted a guideline for the use of the program allowance). For the orientation of applicants, the results and final reports of the first funding round are published [here](#). We expect projects to run for approximately six months. At the end of the term, projects are required to document their results, especially with regard to data publication that has taken place or is planned. Funding is provided within the framework of a transfer contract. A corresponding draft contract can be viewed [here](#). In the context of the application, reference is made to the following templates for the [application text](#) and the [calculation](#). In any case, it is recommended to involve the respective administrations in the application process at an early stage.

Please send your application to fdi-office@lifbi.de.

- Deadline for applications: September 30th, 2023
- Notice of granting: End of June 2024
- Start of funding period: October 1st, 2024 or later

Contact

For more information, please visit <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/konsortswd/the-consortium/services/rdm-grants/> and feel free to contact

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Who we are

A3 Detailed work steps from the applications

Organizational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drafting and concluding a data transfer agreement (between data owner & RDC) • Preparing a data management plan (in some cases for ongoing surveys with the benefit of conducting future survey waves & providing future data in a standardized way) • Clarifying all data rights issues • Creating an access concept for a particularly sensitive data product
Data update or extension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By newer time points • By additional information (e.g. of geographical type like postal code & location of respondents or administrative data like employment history) • Constructing weights • Creating trend data sets that contain measurement invariant scaling of scales • Searching for other thematically similar data sets from other data owners with the aim of publishing a thematic open data database • Creating harmonized variables for identical constructs from different data sets
Data preparation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitizing sources (including work in archives on site = travel expenses) • Generating auxiliary variables • Re-coding open data (from quantitative surveys or video recordings using standardized vocabulary) • Creating a schema for missing values • Correcting and assigning missing categories • Correcting spelling errors • Correcting implausible values • Reviewing filter routing (and assignment of appropriate missing values) • Labeling & re-coding inverse items • Consistent naming of scales, labels, values within one data set • Standardizing variables and labels across different data sets of a research project • Harmonizing different data sets (identification, consistent naming and specific storage of harmonized variables in new data set = new data product) • Checking for up-to-dateness & completeness of text collections • Deleting duplicate files in data collections • Standardizing and completing text collections like country reports and derivation of (quantitative) indicators from them • Methodological assessment: Reviewing potential changes for future surveys • Processing complex log file data by extracting meaningful information from a wealth of existing log file data and making it usable • Cutting video and audio material into appropriate sequences (e.g. by individual case) • Connecting different materials (video/audio/transcripts/memos/log-event-data) of one case • Converting original material into other (memory/software) formats
Anonymization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating an anonymization concept for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ a data set, ◦ web tracking data, ◦ merging of sensitive data sets including verification of legal requirements • Performing anonymization for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ text or audio recordings, ◦ open text data in surveys, ◦ quantitative data, e.g. by aggregating or deleting data if necessary, ◦ video recordings by means of adaptation, optimization and application of face-recognizing software • Replacing pseudonymous data with random numbers • Tasks explicitly carried out at an RDC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ checking anonymization by RDC staff & if necessary run anonymization by RDC staff; if necessary with legal advice for qualitative data, ◦ allocating access levels after review of the material
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting inventory of data material (for qualitative projects with different locations, times, types of data) • Creating a documentation concept (for extensive projects with different materials and data types) • Creating documentation of the data collection process (e.g. on sampling, fieldwork) like a field or technical report • Comparing existing documentation with the RDC standards and, if necessary, adapting documentation to the RDC standards

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating or expanding a codebook (also: checking legal aspects – which formulations may be used in the codebook (copyright for psychometric items), which sources may only be referred to)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a variable report (=codebook & descriptive evaluations)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a scale manual (=codebook & calculation of item and scale characteristics)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a data manual
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating an overview of the constructs in the panel process for panel surveys
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contextualizing the data
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting data corpus (data collection process & discussion of sources used)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting data sources (creation of a bibliography, expert interview as source if applicable)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating metadata documentation (e.g. labeling of variables; e.g. according to DDI standard)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translation (of codebook, metadata, data, field reports, etc.) into English
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing research field-specific ontology standards and data structures for the construction of an open data database
Publication of the data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI registration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing data as Scientific Use File (SUF)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing accompanying materials
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing information on data on the RDC website
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating & publishing data on a platform of its own, but belonging to the RDC/repository (cloned unit)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualizing data in an existing monitoring system
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describing data access
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizing a data workshop for data users
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presenting the data set at conferences; in networks of RDC
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing a data feature/description of the data set for a professional journal (description of content concepts & data)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing data documentation as a discussion paper of the publishing institution
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing a white paper on anonymization of web tracking data
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a workflow for automatic preparation & documentation of future studies (waves) (for multi-wave surveys that have not yet been completed; for similar cross-sectional surveys)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsequent obtaining of informed consent for secondary use after data collection had been completed (partly after transmission of pseudonymized data)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining update modalities of openly accessible time series data

Note: The list contains specific work steps from the applications of round 1 and round 2

A4. Transfer contract

Vertrag über die Weiterleitung von Mitteln

zwischen dem

Leibniz-Institut für Bildungsverläufe e.V. (LifBi),
Wilhelmsplatz 3, 96047 Bamberg
vertreten durch xxxxxxxxxxxx,

– im Folgenden: „LifBi“ –

und

xxxxx
xxxxxxxxx
vertreten xxxxxxxx,

– im Folgenden: „xx“ –

Bund und Länder haben am 26. November 2018 eine Verwaltungsvereinbarung getroffen, im Rahmen eines gemeinsamen Projektes den Aufbau einer Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) finanziell zu fördern. Mit dem NFDI-Projekt soll die Wettbewerbsfähigkeit des Wissenschaftsstandorts Deutschland nachhaltig gestärkt werden.

Die Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskonferenz (GWK) hat in ihrer Sitzung am 26.06.2020 die Einrichtung des Konsortiums für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften (KonsortSWD) zum 01.10.2020 beschlossen. KonsortSWD als Teil der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) unterstützt Forschende dabei, ihre Daten für die Sekundärnutzung zu erschließen und bereitzustellen.

KonsortSWD hat sich zum Ziel gesetzt, die bestehende Dateninfrastruktur zur Beforschung der Gesellschaft zu stärken, zu erweitern und zu vertiefen. Unter Berücksichtigung der Bedürfnisse der wissenschaftlichen Gemeinschaft und der einschlägigen Fachgesellschaften soll die Dateninfrastruktur transparent, service- und nutzungsorientiert gestaltet sein.

Zu den Aufgaben von KonsortSWD zählt, die Nachnutzungspotenziale der unterschiedlichen Typen von Forschungsdaten auszubauen und Forschenden bei der Umsetzung eines geeigneten Forschungsdatenmanagement-Plans in ihren Projekten behilflich zu sein.

Auf Grundlage des KonsortSWD Mittelweiterleitungs- und Kooperationsvertrages führt das LfBi die „Fördermittel Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM)“ durch. Dieser Mittelweiterleitungs- und Kooperationsvertrag bildet die Grundlage für den Weiterleitungsvertrag zwischen dem LfBi und XXXX, an den/die das LfBi den im Finanzierungsplan festgelegten Anteil weiterleitet.

Gegenstand des Fördermittels ist ein kompetitives Antragsverfahren. Die Begutachtung der eingegangenen Anträge erfolgte durch die Gremien des KonsortSWD, insb. durch den ständigen Ausschuss für Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (FDI).

Die dem LfBi zugesagte Zuwendung ist aufgrund des Mittelweiterleitungs- und Kooperationsvertrages mit Auflagen und Bedingungen verbunden, die Bestandteil des Mittelweiterleitungs- und Kooperationsvertrages sind und mit diesem Weiterleitungsvertrag verbindlich an XXXX weitergegeben werden.

Dies vorangeschickt, vereinbaren die Vertragsparteien das Folgende:

§ 1

Zuwendungszweck und Vertragsgegenstand

- (1) Die mit diesem Weiterleitungsvertrag verbundene Zuwendung darf nur für _____ in dem Sinne verwendet werden, wie dies nach Art und Umfang im Antrag des/der _____ vom _____ sowie dem dort beigefügten Projekt- und Finanzierungsplan beschrieben worden ist.
- (2) Gegenstand des vorliegenden Weiterleitungsvertrages ist die Weiterleitung von Zuwendungen zur Durchführung des in § 1 Abs. 1 aufgeführten Projekts.
- (3) Grundlage der Zusammenarbeit sind die Verwendungsrichtlinien – Bedingungen für Förderverträge mit der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft e.V. über Konsortien im Rahmen der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (im Folgenden: „Verwendungsrichtlinien“) in der jeweils aktuellen Fassung sowie die zugrundeliegenden Anträge an das LfBi, insbesondere die einem Förderantrag zugrundeliegenden Arbeitspläne. Die Verwendungsrichtlinien, ebenso wie der Förderantrag vom _____ sind integrale Bestandteile dieses Vertrags und diesem Vertrag als Anlage beigefügt.
- (4) Die Vertragsparteien verwenden für Zwecke dieses Weiterleitungsvertrages die den Verwendungsrichtlinien niedergelegten Vorgaben der Förderung. Sie akzeptieren insbesondere das Prüfungsrecht der DFG nach Maßgabe der Ziffer 7 der Verwendungsrichtlinien, darüberhinausgehend beispielsweise die Vorgaben zu den Bewirtschaftungsgrundsätzen, die Zweckbindung der Fördermittel und den Katalog nichtabrechenbarer Ausgaben. Die/der/das _____ verpflichtet sich, das LfBi während der gesamten Vertragslaufzeit (§ 10) tatkräftig und mit bestem Wissen und Gewissen darin zu unterstützen, dass das LfBi seine Nachweis- und Berichtspflichten gegenüber dem Zuwendungsgeber und der DFG, die sich aus den Verwendungsrichtlinien ergeben, vollumfänglich und fristgerecht erfüllen kann.

§ 2

Mittelverwendung durch den/die _____

- (1) Die Mittel, die xxx vom LfBi erhält, sind zweckgebunden. XXX darf die Mittel, die er/sie vom LfBi bezieht, nur für Ausgaben verwenden, die zur Erfüllung seiner/ihrer Aufgaben des in § 1 Abs. 1 aufgeführten Projekts nach Maßgabe des Aufgaben- und Finanzplans vom _____ erforderlich und von den Verwendungsrichtlinien gedeckt sind.
- (2) Die weitergeleiteten Mittel sind sparsam und wirtschaftlich zu verwenden.
- (3) Soweit _____ erhaltene Mittel für die Erfüllung ihrer/seiner Aufgaben gemäß Aufgaben- und Finanzplan nicht benötigt, werden diese auf den Mittelbedarf der folgenden Mittelanforderung angerechnet; die Anrechnung ist in der folgenden Mittelanforderung auszuweisen. Nach dem Ende der Vertragslaufzeit (§ 10) hat _____ erhaltene, aber nicht für das in § 1 Abs. 1 aufgeführte Projekt verbrauchte Mittel unaufgefordert innerhalb von 30 Banktagen an das LfBi zurückzuüberweisen. Satz 2 gilt nicht für Beträge, die aufgrund bewirkter Leistung bis zum Ende der Vertragslaufzeit dem Grunde und der Höhe nach feststehen, die tatsächliche Auszahlung nach Maßgabe des zugrundeliegenden Rechtsverhältnisses jedoch erst

nach dem Ende der Vertragslaufzeit erfolgt und die fristgerechte Begleichung einer Forderung durch die Rückzahlung gefährdet wäre.

- (4) Ausgaben der/des _____ nach Absatz 1 Satz 1, die den auf die/das _____ entfallenden Anteil an Fördermitteln übersteigen, sind von der/dem _____ selbst aus eigenen Mitteln zu tragen; es besteht keine Nachschusspflicht der LfBi.
- (5) Verwendet _____ einen an sie/ihn weitergeleiteten Förderbetrag trotz schriftlicher Rüge durch das LfBi nicht im Einklang mit Verwendungsrichtlinien und/oder nicht im Einklang mit dem Finanz- und Arbeitsplan und/oder nicht im Einklang mit diesem Weiterleitungsvertrag, hat das LfBi gegen _____ einen Anspruch auf Erstattung der nachweislich fehlverwendeten Mittel. Ein Erstattungsanspruch des LfBi entsteht und wird fällig, sobald eine entsprechende Aufforderung nebst Zahlungsziel der/dem _____ zugegangen ist.
- (6) Der/die/das _____ nimmt zur Kenntnis, dass das LfBi berechtigt ist, seine Rückzahlungsansprüche gegen _____ an den Zuwendungsgeber und die DFG abzutreten.
- (7) Hinsichtlich der Verwendung der Mittel als Personal-, Sach- und Investitionsmittel gelten die Vorgaben der Verwendungsrichtlinien der DFG entsprechend. Dies gilt insbesondere auch für die Vorgaben der DFG zur Nennung des LfBi oder einer anderen eindeutigen Zuordnung sowie der Art der Tätigkeit in Arbeitsverträgen.

§ 3

Nachweis- und Aufbewahrungspflichten

- (1) _____ verpflichtet sich gegenüber dem LfBi die Verwendung der Mittel, die _____ vom LfBi bezieht, detailliert nachzuweisen.
- (2) Art und Umfang der Rechnungslegung des/der _____ gegenüber dem LfBi ergeben sich in entsprechender Anwendung der Ziffer 6 und der Ziffer 12 der Verwendungsrichtlinien der DFG. Die Dokumentation gegenüber dem LfBi erfolgt digital. Das LfBi wird _____ entsprechende digitale Formulare zur Verfügung stellen.
- (3) _____ nimmt das Recht der Zuwendungsgebers und der DFG, auf Grundlage der Ziffer 7 der Verwendungsrichtlinien, Prüfungen beim LfBi vorzunehmen, zur Kenntnis. _____ verpflichtet sich gegenüber dem LfBi, diesem vollumfänglich und fristgemäß Nachweise zu erbringen, die das LfBi zur Erfüllung seiner eigenen Nachweis- und Berichtspflichten gegenüber der DFG benötigt. Beispielsweise muss _____ in den dem LfBi vorzulegenden Abrechnungsunterlagen die Gründe für eine Umdisposition von Personal- und Sachkosten festhalten (Ziffer 2.6.2 der Verwendungsrichtlinien der DFG).
- (4) _____ legt dem LfBi die erforderlichen Nachweise unaufgefordert spätestens am 28. Februar des folgenden Jahres vor.

- (5) _____ hat die dem LfBi vorzulegenden Abrechnungsunterlagen nebst Belegen mindestens zehn Jahre ab dem rechnerischen Abschluss eines jeweiligen Haushaltsjahres aufzubewahren. Davon unberührt bleibt die Pflicht zur längeren Aufbewahrung nach anderen Vorschriften.
- (6) Erfüllt _____ die Nachweispflichten nicht, nicht vollständig oder nicht rechtzeitig, ist das LfBi berechtigt, die Weiterleitung weiterer Mittel an _____ zu verweigern (Zurückbehaltungsrecht).

§ 4 Mitteilungspflichten

- (1) _____ verpflichtet sich gegenüber dem LfBi, alle wesentlichen zur Durchführung dieses Vertrags notwendigen Informationen regelmäßig und ohne Aufforderung mitzuteilen. Dazu gehört insbesondere die Mitteilung solcher Umstände, die Geschäftsgrundlage dieses Vertrags geworden sind, beispielsweise Angaben zur Projektleitung. Die Mitteilung kann in Textform, d.h. auch per E-Mail, erfolgen.
- (2) _____ teilt dem LfBi unaufgefordert und schriftlich mit Namen und Kontaktdaten (inkl. Email) einer administrativen Ansprechperson, insb. für die Mittelweiterleitung.
- (3) _____ erteilt auf erstes Anfordern die erbetenen Informationen, soweit diese zur Durchführung dieses Vertrags notwendig sind oder soweit das LfBi sie benötigt, um ihre eigenen Berichtspflichten gegenüber dem Zuwendungsgeber und der DFG im Zusammenhang mit dem NFDI-Projekt zu erfüllen.

§ 5 Rücktrittsrecht des LfBi; Schadensersatz

- (1) Das LfBi behält sich vor, von diesem Vertrag ganz oder teilweise zurückzutreten,
1. wenn ihm nicht die zur Weiterleitung an _____ bestimmten Mittel zur Verfügung gestellt werden, ohne dass Gründe vorliegen, die das LfBi zu vertreten hat,
 2. wenn _____ innerhalb eines Jahres nach Abschluss dieses Vertrags keine Fördermittel vom LfBi abgerufen hat,
 3. wenn _____ den vertraglichen Pflichten – insbesondere Verwendungs-, Nachweis- und Mitteilungspflichten – nach zweifacher erfolgloser schriftlicher Rüge des LfBi nicht in angemessener Zeit vollständig erfüllt

oder

4. soweit ein wirksamer Rücktritt von dem mit dem LfBi geschlossenen Mittelweiterleitungs- und Kooperationsvertrag erfolgt.

Gesetzliche Rücktrittsrechte des LfBi bleiben unberührt. Der Rücktritt erfolgt durch schriftliche Erklärung gegenüber dem anderen Teil.

- (2) Die Abwicklung des Rücktritts erfolgt nach den gesetzlichen Vorschriften. Ein Anspruch des LfBi auf Erstattung oder Wertersatz ist jährlich mit 5 Prozentpunkten über dem jeweiligen Basiszinssatz der Europäischen Zentralbank zu verzinsen. Der Zinslauf beginnt vorbehaltlich des Satzes 4 nach Ablauf von einem Monat ab Zugang der Rücktrittserklärung. In den Fällen des Absatzes 1 Satz 1 Nummer 4 beginnt der Zinslauf mit Ablauf des Tages, an dem der Verwendungsnachweis abzugeben ist. Der Zinslauf endet mit Ablauf des Tages, der dem Tag vorausgeht, an dem der zurückzuzahlende Betrag auf einem Bankkonto des LfBi eingeht.
- (3) Schadensersatzansprüche der Vertragsparteien untereinander wegen behaupteter Mängel oder Verzugs in der fachlichen Arbeit sind ausgeschlossen.

§ 6

Signalisation nach außen

- (1) Im Rechtsverkehr nach außen tritt nur jede einzelne Vertragspartei – jeweils nur im eigenen Namen und auf eigene Rechnung – auf.
- (2) Sofern eine Vertragspartei im Rechtsverkehr nach außen auftritt – bspw. Verträge mit Auftragnehmerninnen oder Auftragnehmern und/oder Datennutzenden schließt, Publikationen herausgibt oder Stellenausschreibungen veröffentlicht –, hat sie durch Verwendung eindeutiger Bezeichnungen und Abbildungen von Logos sicherzustellen, dass nur sie in eigener Person und nicht auch LfBi rechtlich berechtigt und verpflichtet ist. Dies gilt auch bei der Gestaltung einer Website, eines Impressums i.S. des § 5 Telemediengesetz (TMG) und von E-Mail-Signaturen.

§ 7

Regeln guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis;

Verfahren bei wissenschaftlichem Fehlverhalten

- (1) Die Vertragsparteien erkennen für sich und ihre wissenschaftlichen und wissenschafts-akzessorischen Beschäftigten die Grundsätze der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis, wie sie insbesondere im Kodex „Leitlinien zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis“ der DFG niedergelegt sind, an.
- (2) Die weiteren in den Verwendungsrichtlinien niedergelegten Vorgaben der DFG bei wissenschaftlichem Fehlverhalten gelten im Verhältnis zwischen dem LfBi und XXXX entsprechend.

§ 8 Vertraulichkeit

- (1) Die Vertragsparteien werden als vertraulich gekennzeichnete oder erkennbar vertrauliche Informationen anderer Vertragsparteien, die ihnen im Rahmen des Projekts bekannt werden, vorbehaltlich des Absatzes 2 nicht an Dritte weitergeben. Diese Pflicht besteht auch nach Beendigung dieses Vertrags (§ 10 Abs. 2).

- (2) Die Pflicht zur Wahrung von Vertraulichkeit besteht nicht
 1. im Verhältnis _____ zum LfBi, zum Zuwendungsgeber und zur DFG, soweit beide genannten Institutionen Informationen benötigen, um ihre eigenen Nachweispflichten gegenüber dem Zuwendungsgeber und der DFG bzw. gegenüber dem Bund und den Ländern zu erfüllen,
 2. im Verhältnis einer jeden Vertragspartei zum Bund und zu den Ländern,
 3. im Verhältnis der Vertragsparteien untereinander in Bezug auf Informationen, die
 - a) vor der Weitergabe allgemein zugänglich sind oder als der Öffentlichkeit bereits bekannt gelten,
 - b) der Öffentlichkeit nach der Weitergabe ohne Mitwirken oder Verschulden einer betroffenen Vertragspartei bekannt oder allgemein zugänglich werden,
 - c) dem Empfänger bei Erhalt der Information bereits bekannt warenoder
 - d) Informationen entsprechen, die dem Empfänger zu irgendeinem Zeitpunkt von einem Dritten ohne Auferlegung einer Vertraulichkeitsverpflichtung offenbart oder zugänglich gemacht werden oder von einem Mitarbeiter des Empfängers ohne Kenntnis der Information entwickelt wurden,sowie
 4. im Verhältnis zu Gerichten und Behörden, soweit diese die Offenlegung von Informationen anordnen.

Die interne Weitergabe nach Absatz 1 vertraulicher Informationen durch die empfangende Vertragspartei ist nur insoweit gestattet, als dies für das Projekt erforderlich (need-to-know) und sichergestellt ist, dass nur die Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter die geheimhaltungsbedürftigen Informationen erhalten, denen im Rahmen der rechtlichen Möglichkeiten gleichwertige Geheimhaltungspflichten auferlegt wurden.

§ 9
Konfliktlösung

- (1) Die Vertragsparteien werden sich nach bestem Wissen und Gewissen bemühen, etwaige auftretende Streitigkeiten, die sich aus diesem Vertrag oder über seine Gültigkeit ergeben, gütlich beizulegen. Sofern eine gütliche Streitbeilegung nicht möglich ist, werden Streitigkeiten vorzugsweise nach der Schiedsgerichtsordnung der deutschen Institution für Schiedsgerichtsbarkeit e.V. (DIS) unter Ausschluss des ordentlichen Rechtsweges endgültig entschieden. Das Schiedsgericht besteht aus einem Einzelschiedsrichter. Der Schiedsort ist Bamberg.
- (2) Für Ansprüche aus diesem Vertrag sowie für Ansprüche des LfBi gegen _____ auf Erfüllung der vertraglichen Nachweis- und Berichtspflichten steht alternativ der Rechtsweg zu den ordentlichen Gerichten offen.

§ 10
Dauer des Vertrags, Kündigung

- (1) Der Vertrag tritt mit Unterzeichnung durch die Vertragsparteien mit Wirkung zum xx.xx.2021 in Kraft.
- (2) Die Laufzeit des Vertrags endet mit der vollständigen Erledigung der Aufgaben der Vertragsparteien gemäß Arbeits- und Finanzplan Fassung und der vollständigen Erfüllung aller Pflichten der _____ gegenüber dem LfBi, insbesondere aller Pflichten zur Erbringung von Nachweisen über die Mittelverwendung, spätestens jedoch mit Ablauf des _____.
- (3) Jede Vertragspartei kann diesen Vertrag mit Wirkung für und gegen sich mit einer Frist von drei Monaten aus wichtigem Grund kündigen. Ein wichtiger Grund liegt insbesondere vor, wenn die Weiterarbeit für die Vertragspartei unzumutbar geworden ist, eine im Förderantrag genannte Person nicht länger bei der Vertragspartei beschäftigt ist oder die Förderung nachträglich wesentlich verringert oder widerrufen wurde. Die Kündigung bedarf einer schriftlichen Erklärung gegenüber dem LfBi.
- (4) Beendet _____ diesen Vertrag, so erstattet er/sie alle zum Zeitpunkt der Wirksamkeit der Kündigung noch nicht nach Maßgabe des Aufgaben- und Finanzplans verausgabten weitergeleiteten Mittel binnen acht Wochen an das LfBi zurück. Demgegenüber erhält _____ die Restmittel, die ihm/ihr nach Vorlage eines Nachweises bis zum Beendigungszeitpunkt des Vertrags noch zustehen.

§ 11
Schlussbestimmungen

- (1) Sollten einzelne Bestimmungen dieses Vertrages unwirksam oder undurchführbar sein oder nach Vertragsschluss unwirksam oder undurchführbar werden, bleibt die Wirksamkeit des Vertrages im Übrigen unberührt. An die Stelle der unwirksamen oder undurchführbaren Bestimmung soll diejenige wirksame und durchführbare Regelung treten, deren Wirkungen der wirtschaftlichen Zielsetzung möglichst nahekommen, die die Vertragsparteien mit der unwirksamen beziehungsweise undurchführbaren Bestimmung verfolgt haben.
- (2) Änderungen dieses Vertrags bedürfen der Schriftform. Dies gilt auch für die Änderung des Satzes 1. Dabei genügt es, wenn den anderen Vertragsparteien jeweils eine bildliche Wiedergabe des Vertrages mit der originalen Unterschrift in Form einer PDF-Datei per E-Mail übersandt wird.
- (3) Dieser Vertrag unterliegt dem Recht der Bundesrepublik Deutschland unter Ausschluss des UN-Kaufrechts.
- (4) Erfüllungsort für alle Zahlungen ist, soweit gemäß § 29 Abs. 2 ZPO zulässig, Bamberg. Gerichtsstand für Streitigkeiten gemäß § 15 Abs. 2 ist, soweit gemäß § 29 Abs. 2 und § 38 Abs. 1 ZPO, zulässig, Bamberg.

Für das LfBi:

.....
Ort, Datum

.....
NAME, Funktion

Für XXXXX:

.....
Ort, Datum

.....
NAME, Funktion

A5. Overview of all projects

TITLE	B-STA-R: Bilateral Science and Technology Agreements Repository
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.07.2021 - 31.08.2021
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nicolas Rüffin (WZB)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GESIS
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Preparation, documentation, and provision of a research data set on bilateral scientific and technical agreements (1937–2020)
FINAL REPORT	Rüffin, N. (2021). <i>Abschlussbericht B-STA-R: Bilateral Science and Technology Agreements Repository Eine Vertragsdatenbank für Forschende in den Sozial- und Geisteswissenschaften</i> . https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_B-STA-R-.pdf
DATA	<p>Rüffin, N. (2021). <i>B-STA-R: A repository for bilateral science and technology agreements</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozialforschung. https://doi.org/10.7802/2310</p> <p>The B-STA-R data set comprises 1,138 bilateral agreements on science and technology cooperations (including follow-up agreements) between predominantly G20 and OECD countries from 1937 to 2020 and has made this information freely available under CC BY 4.0 since 2021. It contains data on contract years, terms, entry into force, full texts, and data collection and selection, thus providing a basis for research in the fields of international relations, science studies, foreign science policy, and history.</p>
TITLE	CILS4NEPS: Harmonizing and Combining Data from the Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries with Data from the Starting Cohort 4 of the National Educational Panel Study
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.07.2021 - 30.06.2022
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dr. Jörg Dollmann (MZES, University of Mannheim) Andreas Horr (LifBi)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDC-LifBi
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Combining and merging the NEPS SC4 and CILS4EU data sets
FINAL REPORT	<p>Dollmann, J., & Horr, A. (2022). <i>Bericht zum Forschungsvorhaben „Harmonisierung und Zusammenführen der Daten des Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries (CILS4EU) mit den Daten der Startkohorte 4 des Nationalen Bildungspanels (NEPS)“—CILS4NEPS</i> -. https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_CILS4NEPS.pdf</p> <p>Dollmann, J., Arnold, L., & Horr, A. (2025). CILS4NEPS – Unlocking Research Potential Through More Participants, More Schools and International Comparison: Harmonized Data for Research on Education, School-to-work Transition and Integration Processes for Adolescents in Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden and England. <i>Jahrbücher Für Nationalökonomie Und Statistik</i>, 245(1–2), 215–234. https://doi.org/10.1515/jbnst-2024-0016</p>
DATA	<p>Dollmann, J., Horr, A., Arnold, L., Kerzner, V., Schmidt, R., Weber, F., & Weißmann, M. (2023). <i>A Harmonised Dataset Based on CILS4EU and NEPS SC4, Scientific Use File</i> (Version 1.0) [Dataset]. Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories. https://doi.org/10.5157/CILS4NEPS:SUF:1.0</p> <p>CILS4NEPS is offered jointly by the Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries Project (CILS4EU), based at the Mannheim Centre for European Social Research (MZES), the Oxford University, the Universities of Utrecht and Tilburg, and the SOFI at Stockholm University, and the National Educational Panel Study (NEPS), based at the Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories in Bamberg (LifBi). CILS4NEPS provides researchers with a harmonized data set that combines information from CILS4EU (waves 1-3) and the NEPS Starting Cohort 4 (waves 1-6).</p>

TITLE	CILS4NEPS-E: Harmonizing and Combining Data from the Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries with Data from the Starting Cohort 4 of the National Educational Panel Study - Extension
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2023
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01.10.2024 – 31.03.2025
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Andreas Horr (LifBi) • Dr. Jörg Dollmann (MZES) • Lena Arnold (MZES)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDC-LifBi
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Extension of the CILS4NEPS project, combining and merging further waves and measurements of the NEPS SC4 and CILS4EU data sets
FINAL REPORT	<p>Arnold, L., Dollmann, J., & Horr, A. (2025). <i>Bericht zum Forschungsvorhaben „Harmonisierte Daten der Startkohorte 4 (SC4) des Nationalen Bildungspanels (NEPS) und des Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries (CILS4EU) – Erweiterung“—CILS4NEPS-E - im Rahmen der Projektförderung Forschungsdatenmanagement durch das Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs-, und Wirtschaftswissenschaften (KonsortSWD)</i>. Available upon request by the authors</p> <p>Arnold, L., Horr, A., Bauer, M., Finke, B., & Dollmann, J. (2006). <i>Harmonisierung und Zusammenführung der Daten des Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries (CILS4EU) mit den Daten der Startkohorte 4 des Nationalen Bildungspanel (NEPS) – CILS4NEPS</i>. KonsortSWD Working Paper 16/2026. Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften (KonsortSWD – NFDI4Society). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1912908</p>
DATA	<i>Data publication planned for 2026</i>
TITLE	Mobile Knowledge: The Glocalization of Medical Professional Knowledge and Professional Practice (Glopro)
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01.07.2021 - 30.11.2021
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Anja Weiß (University of Duisburg-Essen)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDC Qualiservice, University of Bremen
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Preparation and provision of transnational video and transcript data from the Glopro project for qualitative secondary analyses
FINAL REPORT	<p>Weiß, A., & Hollstein, B. (2022). <i>KonsortSWD - Research Data Grants—Abschlussbericht für die kooperative Aufbereitung der Forschungsmaterialien des Projekts „Mobiles Wissen: Die Glokalisierung von medizinischem professionellem Wissen und professioneller Praxis“ (Glopro) für die Archivierung und Sekundärnutzung im Rahmen der KonsortSWD Research Data Grants</i>. https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_Glopro.pdf</p> <p>Weiß, A., Quasinowski, B., & Sommer, I. (2022). <i>Study Report “Globalizing medical knowledge and practice”. Transcripts, translation, audiovisual and context material for doctor-patient-interaction videoobserved at university hospitals in Ankara (Turkey), Beijing (PRChina), Groningen (Netherlands) and Würzburg (Germany)</i> (S. 36). Universität Bremen. https://doi.org/10.26092/ELIB/1395</p>
DATA	<p>Sommer, I., Weingartz, S., Elçin, M., Tuncel, B., & Weiß, A. (2021). <i>Globalizing medical knowledge and practise: Doctor-patient-interaction videoobserved at a university hospital in Ankara (Turkey). Transcripts, translation, audiovisual and context material</i> (S. 1430 data points) [Text/tab-separated-values]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939234</p> <p>Weiß, A., Sommer, I., Chen, W., Liu, T., Guo, F., & Liu, W. (2021). <i>Globalizing medical knowledge and practise. Doctor-patient-interaction videoobserved at a university hospital in Beijing (PRChina)</i>.</p>

Transcripts, translation, audiovisual and context material (S. 1930 data points) [Text/tab-separated-values]. PANGAEA. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939235>

Weiß, A., Sommer, I., Merse, S., Störk, S., Breunig, M., & Morbach, C. (2021). *Globalizing medical knowledge and practise. Doctor-patient-interaction videoobserved at a university hospital in Würzburg (Germany). Transcripts, translation, audiovisual and context material* (S. 850 data points) [Text/tab-separated-values]. PANGAEA. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939245>

Weiß, A., Sommer, I., Merse, S., Weingartz, S., Wietasch, G., Maass, A., & Assa, S. (2021). *Globalizing medical knowledge and practise. Doctor-patient-interaction videoobserved at a university hospital in Groningen (Netherlands). Transcripts, translation, audiovisual and context material* (S. 1360 data points) [Text/tab-separated-values]. PANGAEA. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939238>

The Glopro data sets provide audiovisual data and transcripts on physician and patient interactions from Turkey, China, the Netherlands and Germany that enable sustainable reuse and allow for a wide range of analyses in various fields.

TITLE	Health Behavior and Injuries in School Age
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.07.2021 - 30.06.2022
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prof. Dr. Andreas Klocke (Research Centre of Demographic Change (FZDW) at Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDC-LifBi
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Data preparation, documentation, and provision of panel survey data
FINAL REPORT	Klocke, A., & Fuß, D. (2022). <i>Abschlussbericht zum Vorhaben Aufbereitung, Dokumentation und Bereitstellung des Datenkorpus der Panelstudie „Gesundheitsverhalten und Unfallgeschehen im Schulalter“ (GUS) im Rahmen der Projektförderung „Forschungsdatenmanagement“ durch das Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs-, und Wirtschaftswissenschaften (KonsortSWD)</i> . https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_GUS.pdf
DATA	<p>Klocke, A., & Fuß, D. (2022). <i>Abschlussbericht zum Vorhaben Aufbereitung, Dokumentation und Bereitstellung des Datenkorpus der Panelstudie „Gesundheitsverhalten und Unfallgeschehen im Schulalter“ (GUS) im Rahmen der Projektförderung „Forschungsdatenmanagement“ durch das Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs-, und Wirtschaftswissenschaften (KonsortSWD)</i>. https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_GUS.pdf</p> <p>The data from the survey of more than 10,000 pupils in grades 5 to 10, which was conducted in six waves, supplemented by information from head teachers and interviewers, offers the scientific community a great potential for analysis at the intersection of education and school research as well as risk, accident, injury and health research.</p>

TITLE	Language Situation at the Inner-German Border
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.09.2021 - 30.06.2022
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dr. Nicole Palliwoda (University of Siegen) Prof. Dr. Alexander Werth (University of Passau)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archive for Spoken German (Archiv für Gesprochenes Deutsch, AGD) at Leibniz Institute for the German language (IDS)
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Data curation and provision from two projects on language and personal data
FINAL REPORT	Palliwoda, N., & Werth, A. (2022). <i>Sprachsituation an der innerdeutschen Grenze. Abschlussbericht</i> . https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_SPRIG.pdf
DATA	Palliwoda, N. (2025). <i>Korpus „Sprechen über die ehemalige innerdeutsche Grenze“ (SEIG)</i> [Dataset]. Archiv für Gesprochenes Deutsch (AGD). https://agd.ids-mannheim.de/SEIG_extern.shtml

Palliwoda, N., & Werth, A. (2025). *Korpus „Sprachsituation an der innerdeutschen Grenze“ (SPIG) [Dataset]*. Archiv für Gesprochenes Deutsch (AGD). https://agd.ids-mannheim.de/SPIG_extem.shtml

Development and provision of data from two projects on the language situation at the inner-German border for secondary use. The material serves the research interests of dialectology, language change research and language sociology. In addition, there are cross-disciplinary links to research questions in sociology (e.g. socio-biography), history (especially oral history) and political science (e.g. attitude research). The sociolinguistic corpora on language use at the inner-German border contain audio recordings and transcripts.

TITLE	Paying Attention to Attention: Media Exposure and Opinion Formation in an Age of Information Overload (MEOF)
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.09.2021 - 31.08.2022
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prof. Dr. Simon Munzert (Hertie School)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GESIS
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Preparation and provision of a comparative panel data set from the US and Germany with web tracking data for secondary analyses & development of an anonymization concept for web tracking data
FINAL REPORT	<p>Munzert, S. (2022). <i>KonsortSWD - Research Data Grants—Abschlussbericht für die kooperative Aufbereitung, Archivierung und Publikation der Forschungsmaterialien des Projekts „Paying Attention to Attention: Media Exposure and Opinion Formation in an Age of Information Overload“ (MEOF) im Rahmen der KonsortSWD Research Data Grants</i>. https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_MEOF.pdf</p> <p>Munzert, S., Ramirez-Ruiz, S., Watteler, O., Breuer, J., Batzdorfer, V., Eder, C., Wiltshire, D. A., Barberá, P., Guess, A. M., & Yang, J. (2023). <i>Publishing Combined Web Tracking and Survey Data</i>. Open Science Framework. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/y4v8z</p>
DATA	<p>Guess, A. M., Barberá, P., Yang, J., & Munzert, S. (2022). <i>Media Exposure and Opinion Formation in an Age of Information Overload (MEOF) – Survey U.S.A. (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]</i>. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13980</p> <p>Munzert, S., Barberá, P., Guess, A. M., & Yang, J. (2022a). <i>Media Exposure and Opinion Formation in an Age of Information Overload (MEOF) – Survey Germany (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]</i>. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13979</p> <p>Munzert, S., Barberá, P., Guess, A. M., & Yang, J. (2022b). <i>Media Exposure and Opinion Formation in an Age of Information Overload (MEOF) – Webtracking on-site (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]</i>. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13981</p> <p>The data sets provide panel survey data from the US and Germany with web tracking data for scientific reuse. They are relevant for political science, communication studies, media studies, and sociology, with an anonymization concept ensuring the secure use of sensitive web tracking data.</p>

TITLE	MainLife: Development of the Life Story
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.09.2021 - 31.08.2022
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prof. Dr. Tilmann Habermas (Goethe University Frankfurt)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDC Qualiservice, University of Bremen
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Preparation, documentation, and provision of the study "MainLife – Development of Life Story" for scientific reuse
FINAL REPORT	Kemper, N., Mozygemba, K., Habermas, T., & Hollstein, B. (2022). <i>Abschlussbericht zur kooperativen Aufbereitung der Forschungsmaterialien des Projekts „Main- Life—Entwicklung der</i>

	<p><i>Lebensgeschichte“ für die Archivierung und Sekundärnutzung im Rahmen der für die KonsortSWD – Research Data Grants.</i> https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_MainLife.pdf</p>
DATA	<p>Habermas, T. (2022a). <i>MainLife – Life Story Development (quantitative Part)</i> <i>MainLife – Entwicklung der Lebensgeschichte (quantitativer Teil)</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13955</p> <p>Habermas, T. (2022b). <i>MainLife: Entwicklung der Lebensgeschichte. Transkripte der Erzählungen</i> (S. 15861 data points) [Text/tab-separated-values]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.946345</p> <p>The MainLife study combines qualitative life narratives with quantitative data in a 16-year longitudinal study across six cohorts and enables analyses of the development of narrative identity, life reviews, and their connections to personality and well-being for research in psychology, sociology, and linguistics.</p>
TITLE	Anonymization Concept for a Linked Establishment Data Set from Data of the Federal Archives with Data of the IAB
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2021
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01.01.2022 - 31.03.2022
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Sandra Dummert (FDZ-BA/IAB) • Dr. Heiko Stüber (IAB) • Dana Müller (FDZ-BA/IAB)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FDZ-BA/IAB
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Development of an anonymization concept for linking THA/BvS data from the Federal Archives with administrative establishment data from the IAB in compliance with data protection regulations, in order to provide a historical research data set for scientific use
FINAL REPORT	<p>Mackeben, J., Dummert, S., & Müller, D. (2022). <i>ABSCHLUSSBERICHT. Anonymisierungskonzept für einen verknüpften Betriebs- datensatz aus Daten des Bestandes B 412 (THA/BvS) des Bundesarchivs mit den Daten des IAB.</i> https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/Abschlussbericht_Anonymisierungskonzept_BHP_BArch.pdf</p> <p>Diegmann, A., Dummert, S., Gottschalk, S., & Lubczyk, M. (2025). <i>Daten der Treuhandanstalt verknüpft mit dem Betriebs-Historik-Panel des IAB 1989–2023 (THA-BHP 8923)</i> (Nos. 17, 2025 DE; FDZ-DATENREPORT Dokumentation zu Arbeitsmarktdaten). Forschungsdatenzentrum (FDZ) der Bundesagentur für Arbeit (BA) im Institut für Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung (IAB). DOI: 10.5164/IAB.FDZD.2517.de.v1</p>
DATA	<p>Diegmann, A., Dummert, S., Gottschalk, S., & Lubczyk, M. (2025). <i>Daten der Treuhandanstalt verknüpft mit dem Betriebs-Historik-Panel des IAB (THA-BHP) 1989-2023</i> [Dataset]. Das Forschungsdatenzentrum (FDZ) der Bundesagentur für Arbeit (BA) im Institut für Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung (IAB). https://doi.org/10.5164/IAB.THA-BHP8923.DE.EN.V1</p> <p>The data set links the administrative establishment data of the IAB (Establishment History Panel, 1992–2023) with the data of the Treuhandanstalt (THA) and the Federal Agency for Unification-Related Special Tasks (BvS) of the Federal Archives (THA-BHP 8923). It is now possible to identify former GDR companies or their establishments that were privatised by the THA/BvS in the IAB's administrative data. Record linkage procedures were used to link the data.</p>
TITLE	Notified Mass Layoffs
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2023
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01.01.2025 - 31.07.2025
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hannes Walz (IAB and FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FDZ-BA/IAB

PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Creation of an anonymization concept and preparation, linking, documentation and provision of administrative data of companies with mass redundancy notifications and corresponding employment biographies of employees of affected companies
FINAL REPORT	Walz, H. (forthcoming). <i>Notified mass layoffs (Betriebliche Anzeigen zu Massenentlassungen). Abschlussbericht</i> . Forschungsdatenzentrum (FDZ) der Bundesagentur für Arbeit (BA) im Institut für Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung (IAB).
DATA	<i>Data publication planned for 2026</i>
TITLE	20 Years of Protest Survey Data
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2023
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.01.2025 - 30.06.2025
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prof. Dr. Sebastian Haunss (University of Bremen, SOCIUM – Research Center on Inequality and Social Policy) Dr. Piotr Kocyba (Else Frenkel-Brunswik Institute (EFBI), Leipzig University) Dr. Pascal Siegers (GESIS – RDC ALLBUS) Dr. Simon Teune (Freie Universität Berlin)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GESIS
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Preparation, standardization, documentation and provision of survey data from various protests in Germany and Poland.
FINAL REPORT	Haunss, S., Kocyba, P., Siegers, P., Teune, S., Stein, M., & Baumann, H. (2025). <i>20 Jahre Protestbefragungsdaten. Abschlussbericht</i> . KonsortSWD. https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17777997
DATA	<p>Daphi, P., Kocyba, P., Neuber, M., Roose, J., Scholl, F., Rucht, D., Sommer, M., Stuppert, W., Teune, S., & Zajak, S. (2025). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Pegida-Demonstration im Januar 2015 in Dresden</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14672</p> <p>Daphi, P., Meier, L., & Haunss, S. (2025). <i>Demonstrationsbefragungen: Ostermarsch 2022 in Bielefeld</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14649</p> <p>Haunss, S., Daphi, P., Dollbaum, J. M., Grimm, J., & Meier, L. (2025). <i>Demonstrationsbefragungen: Fridays for Future—Globaler Klimastreik am 3. März 2023</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14647</p> <p>Haunss, S., Daphi, P., Teune, S., Stuppert, W., & Zajak, S. (2025). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Demonstration gegen die internationalen Handelsabkommen TTIP und CETA</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14671</p> <p>Haunss, S., Daphi, P., Teune, S., Zajak, S., Gauditz, L., Sommer, M., Knopp, P., Micus, M., & Scharf, P. (2025). <i>Demonstrationsbefragungen: Proteste anlässlich des G20-Treffens 2017 in Hamburg</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14670</p> <p>Haunss, S., Neuber, M., Gardner, B., & Sommer, M. (2025). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Fridays for Future—Globaler Klimastreik am 29. November 2019. Befragungen in Bremen und Berlin</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14657</p> <p>Kocyba, P. (2025a). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Antifaschistische Straßenparty</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14650</p> <p>Kocyba, P. (2025b). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Demo für die Justizreform (Obrońmy naszą suwerenność)</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14655</p> <p>Kocyba, P. (2025c). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Feministischer Protest (Czarny Piątek)</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14667</p> <p>Kocyba, P. (2025d). <i>Demonstrationsbefragung: Feministischer Protest Déjà Vu!</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14669</p>

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- Kocyba, P. (2025e). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Feministischer Protest Manifa* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14663>
- Kocyba, P. (2025f). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Feministischer Protest Manifa* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14668>
- Kocyba, P. (2025g). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Fridays for Future—Globaler Klimastreik am 15. März 2019 (Warschau)* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14677>
- Kocyba, P. (2025h). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Fridays for Future—Globaler Klimastreik am 20. September 2019 (Warschau)* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14659>
- Kocyba, P. (2025i). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Fridays for Future—Globaler Klimastreik am 24. September 2021. Umfrage bei der Demonstration des Młodzieżowy Strajk Klimatyczny (Jugendklimastreik) in Warschau* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14653>
- Kocyba, P. (2025j). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Gedenken an den Absturz der Präsidentenmaschine bei Smoleńsk* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14666>
- Kocyba, P. (2025k). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Gedenken an den Absturz der Präsidentenmaschine bei Smoleńsk (IX rocznica katastrofy smoleńskiej)* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14661>
- Kocyba, P. (2025l). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Heute die Richter—Morgen Du! (Dziś Sędziowie – jutro Ty!)* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14656>
- Kocyba, P. (2025m). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Marsch für die Freiheit (Marsz o Wolność)* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14651>
- Kocyba, P. (2025n). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Marsz Niepodległości (Unabhängigkeitsmarsch)* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14658>
- Kocyba, P. (2025o). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Parada Równości für Toleranz und Gleichberechtigung* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14660>
- Kocyba, P. (2025p). *Demonstrationsbefragung: Parada Równości für Toleranz und Gleichberechtigung von Schwulen und Lesben* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14665>
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The data provide insights into the composition and attitudes of demonstration participants in Germany and Poland for different protests that took place from 2003 to 2023.

TITLE	Crime in the Modern City
TENDER ROUND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2023
PROJECT DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01.10.2024 - 31.07.2025
APPLICANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prof. Dr. Jost Reinecke (University of Bielefeld)
RDC INVOLVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GESIS
PROJECT OBJECTIVE	Preparation, standardization, documentation and provision of longitudinal survey data on youths in Duisburg.
FINAL REPORT	Bendler, J., & Reinecke, J. (2025). <i>Abschlussbericht der Datenarchivierung der kriminologischen Befragung „Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt“</i> (No. 33; Schriftenreihe Jugendkriminalität in der modernen Stadt – Methoden). ISSN 1610-2819
DATA	<p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025a). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2002</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14595</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025b). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2003</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14596</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025c). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2004</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14597</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025d). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2005</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14598</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025e). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2006</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14599</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025f). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2007</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14600</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025g). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2008</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14601</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025h). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2009</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14602</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025i). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2011</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14603</p> <p>Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025j). <i>Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2013</i> (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14604</p>

Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025k). *Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2015* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14605>

Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025l). *Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2017* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14606>

Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025m). *Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2019* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14607>

Boers, K., & Reinecke, J. (2025n). *Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt — Panel* (Version 1.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14608>

The data collection comprises 13 cross-sectional data sets and an extensive panel data set with over 10,000 variables on topics such as delinquency and victimization experiences, as well as parenting and lifestyles. This offers great potential for longitudinal and life course analyses in criminology and the social sciences.

A6. Overview of data sets from the project “20 years of protest surveys”

Year	Titel	Country	doi
2003	Irakkrieg / Iraq War	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14676
2004	Hartz IV / German welfare program for long-term unemployed	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14675
2010	Stuttgart 21 / controversial construction of a new underground through station in the city of Stuttgart	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14674
2014	Montagsmahnwachen / Monday protest vigils	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14673
2015	PEGIDA / Patriotic Europeans Against the Islamization of the Occident	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14672
2015	TTIP / free trade agreement between the EU and the US	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14671
2017	G20 / international forum of 19 countries plus the European Union that works together on global economic issues	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14670
2018	Déjà vu / protests against restricting abortion	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14669
2018	Manifa / protests against restricting abortion	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14668
2018	Czarny Piątek / “Black Friday”, protests against restricting abortion	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14667
2018	Flugzeugabsturz / protests marking the anniversary of the plane crash in Smolensk, where PL president Lech Kaczynski and others died.	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14666
2018	Parada Równości / “Equality march” LGBTQ+ equality march	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14665
2018	Marsz Niepodległości / “Independence march” patriotic parade marking the 100th anniversary of PL regaining independence in 1918	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14664
2019	Manifa / women’s rights	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14663
2019	FFF/März / Fridays for future (March)	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14662
2019	FFF/März / Fridays for future (March)	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14677
2019	Flugzeugabsturz / protests marking the anniversary of the plane crash in Smolensk, where PL president Lech Kaczynski and others died.	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14661
2019	Parada Równości / “Equality march” LGBTQ+ equality march	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14660
2019	FFF/September / Fridays for future (September)	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14659
2019	Marsz Niepodległości / “Independence march” patriotic parade marking Poland’s independence	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14658
2019	FFF/November / Fridays for future (November)	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14657
2019	Justizreform / judicial reform	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14656
2020	Justizreform / judicial reform	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14655
2021	Justizreform / judicial reform	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14654
2021	FFF / Fridays for future	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14653
2021	Oppositionsprotest / opposition-led demonstration	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14652
2021	Impfgegner:innen / anti-vaccination activists	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14651
2021	Antifa	PL	doi.org/10.4232/1.14650
2022	Ostermarschumfrage / Easter Marches – peace demonstrations	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14649
2023	Friedensbewegung/Februar / peace demonstrations (February)	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14648
2023	FFF / Fridays for future	DE	doi.org/10.4232/1.14647
2020	Food for Justice	DE	doi.org/10.7802/2802
2024	Food for Justice	DE	doi.org/10.7802/2783

Note: The last two data sets on Food for Justice are also part of the project’s data collections. They were previously published without KonsortSWD funding.

A7. Overview of data sets from the project "Crime in the modern city"

Year	Titel	City	doi
2002-2019	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt - Panel	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14608
2019	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2019	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14607
2017	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2017	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14606
2015	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2015	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14605
2013	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2013	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14604
2011	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2011	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14603
2009	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2009	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14602
2008	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2008	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14601
2007	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2007	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14600
2006	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2006	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14599
2005	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2005	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14598
2004	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2004	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14597
2003	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2003	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14596
2002	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt 2003	Duisburg	doi.org/10.4232/1.14595
2000-2003	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt. Eine Längsschnittuntersuchung zur Delinquenz von jungen Menschen in Münster – Panelstudie mit 4 Wellen (2000 – 2003)	Münster	doi.org/10.4232/1.13287
2003	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt. Eine Längsschnittuntersuchung zur Delinquenz von jungen Menschen in Münster – Welle 4 (2003)	Münster	doi.org/10.4232/1.13286
2002	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt. Eine Längsschnittuntersuchung zur Delinquenz von jungen Menschen in Münster – Welle 3 (2002)	Münster	doi.org/10.4232/1.13285
2001	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt. Eine Längsschnittuntersuchung zur Delinquenz von jungen Menschen in Münster – Welle 2 (2001)	Münster	doi.org/10.4232/1.13284
2000	Kriminalität in der modernen Stadt. Eine Längsschnittuntersuchung zur Delinquenz von jungen Menschen in Münster – Welle 1 (2000)	Münster	doi.org/10.4232/1.13283

Note: The last five data sets are also part of the project's data collections. They were collected in Münster and previously published without KonsortSWD funding.

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KonsortSWD Working Paper:

KonsortSWD – NFDI4Society, as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure, is expanding offerings to support research with data in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. Our mission is to strengthen, expand and deepen the research data infrastructure for the study of society. It should be user-oriented and consider the needs of the research communities. An important cornerstone is the network of research data centres that has been built up for more than two decades by the German Data Forum (RatSWD). This series contains articles on research data management that are produced in the context of KonsortSWD. Articles that have been externally and double-blind peer-reviewed are marked accordingly.

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